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A Comprehensive Thermo-economic Evaluation and Multi-Criteria Optimization of a Combined MCFC/TEG System

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Citation: Syah, R.; Davarpanah, A.; Nasution, M.K.M.; Tanjung, F.A.; Nezhad, M.M.; Nesaht, M. A Comprehensive Thermo-economic Evaluation and Multi-Criteria Optimization of a Combined MCFC/TEG System. *Sustainability* **2021**, *13*, 13187. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132313187>

Academic Editor: Ahmad Baroutaji

Received: 12 August 2021

Accepted: 22 November 2021

Published: 28 November 2021

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Abstract: In this study, an integrated molten carbonate fuel cell (MCFC), thermoelectric generator (TEG), and regenerator energy system has been introduced and evaluated. MCFC generates power and heating load. The exit fuel gases of the MCFC is separated into three sections: the first section is transferred to the TEG to generate more electricity, the next chunk is conducted to a regenerator to boost the productivity of the suggested plant and compensate for the regenerative destructions, and the last section enters the surrounding. Computational simulation and thermodynamic evaluation of the hybrid plant are carried out utilizing MATLAB and HYSYS software, respectively. Furthermore, a thermo-economic analysis is performed to estimate the total cost of the product and the system cost rate. The offered system is also optimized using multi-criteria genetic algorithm optimization to enhance the exergetic efficiency while reducing the total cost of the product. The power generated by MCFC and TEG is 1247.3 W and 8.37 W, respectively. The result explicates that the provided electricity and provided efficiency of the suggested plant is 1255.67 W and 38%, respectively. Exergy inquiry outcomes betokened that, exergy destruction of the MCFC and TEG is 13,945.9 kW and 262.75 kW, respectively. Furthermore, their exergy efficiency is 68.22% and 97.31%, respectively. The impacts of other parameters like working temperature and pressure, thermal conductance, the configuration of the advantage of the materials, etc., on the thermal and exergetic performance of the suggested system are also evaluated. The optimization outcomes reveal that in the final optimum solution point, the exergetic efficiency and total cost of the product s determined at 70% and 30 USD/GJ.

Keywords: hybrid system; molten carbonates fuel cell; thermoelectric generator; energy; exergy analysis

1. Introduction

In the area of thermal electricity generation, fuel cell technology can be considered a fascinating alternative [1–10] due to their huge potential in diminishing fossil fuel consumption and global warming [11–20]. There are two kinds of fuel cells based on their working temperatures: high-temperature and low-temperature [21–30]. MCFC is considered a high-temperature fuel cell type that is operated at a temperature of 700 °C and has merits such as variation in fuel type, high temperature, and efficiency [31–40], and is commercially available [41–50]. MCFC, like other fuel cells, can generate power and heat in which the thermal energy of the fuel (in our study, natural gas) is converted into power [51–56]. The

high temperature of flue gases of MCFC can be considered another important characteristic of the suggested plant [57–59] which can be used for various applications. One use includes coupling gas turbines with MCFC in hybrid plants [60]. In ref. [61] thermo-economic and environmental aspects of the mentioned hybrid plant were investigated. By adjusting the utilization factor of H_2 , the performance of these integrated systems can be improved [62]. In another investigation, an absorption refrigerator was added to MCFC. That plant had enough potential to generate the needed power and cooling, and its productivity was 3.8% higher than that separated MCFC [63]. Furthermore, MCFC can be used in cogeneration systems. In a system modeled in ref. [64], an MCFC-based cogeneration plant had obtained near-zero-emissions. It is shown that MCFC had the possibility of greenhouse gas emission mitigation and climate change alleviation. As an extraordinary feature, given that the outlet of the anode of MCFC is rich in CO_2 , it is used as a CO_2 separation plant via a CO_2 absorbing procedure [65–67]. With different procedures, such as cryogenic, the mentioned concept has been evaluated in a plethora of studies, and from various standpoints [68–70]. The main aim of all mentioned investigations is to improve the CO_2 absorption ratio and decrease the rate of the exergy destruction cost. As mentioned, the flue gases of MCFC have a high enough temperature, and since $600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is a suitable temperature for thermo-electric generator (TEG) operation, these components can utilize waste heat to generate electricity [71,72]. With the Seebeck effect, the TEGs can generate electricity because of the difference in temperature between cold and hot connectors [73]. In addition, regarding efficiency, this element is less efficient than common engines while being suitable for moderate electricity demand because they are small, reliable, cheap, and safe. With different kinds of fuel cells, the mentioned concept has been scrutinized in an integrated system. An integrated system that includes MCFC and TEG is investigated in ref. [73]. In that plant, power production density and plant efficiency improve by 51% and 20%, respectively, in comparison with the separated MCFC. On the other hand, in another paper, the same system was evaluated with MCFC [74]. In the mentioned study, an improvement in electricity density of 30% has been achieved and a TEC unit generate cooling. In ref. [75] an MCFC coupled with TEG and TEC was intended to produce electricity and a cooling load. Moreover, the electricity density and efficiency were boosted by 3% and 4.1%, respectively, in comparison with the separated fuel cell. The Author in Ref. [76] analyzed a hybrid plant with a fuel cell to increase the productivity of the unit and boost its productivity by 4.5%. Besides, the productivity of the cycle would be improved by 3%, when TEGs are involved [77]. Hasani and Rahbar [78] conducted an experimental evaluation of an integrated system including a 5.1 kW PEMFC with a thermoelectric cooler. The authors utilized four TEC modules and one heat exchanger in their suggested system.

In the current study, a new hybrid process, including MCFC, TEG, and a regenerator is introduced and analyzed by energetic and exergetic analysis approaches for the first time. MCFC has enough potential to generate electricity and heat load. The heat in the flue gases of the MCFC is divided into three categories: the first part is sent to the TEG to generate surplus electricity; the second part is transferred to the regenerator to boost the performance of the plant and compensate the regenerative destructions, and the last part enters the environment. Moreover, Thermodynamic and thermo-economic evaluations of the new hybrid system were conducted by utilizing HYSYS software and Engineering Equation Solver (EES) software. Furthermore, multi-objective optimization with exergetic efficiency and economic objectives simultaneously is carried out by employing EES software and MATLAB which are the other significant novelties of the current work. In fact, according to the best of the authors' knowledge, no systematic study has been carried in terms of economic aspect improvement of the hybrid MCFC/TEG systems. Furthermore, according to the comprehensive parametric study, the impacts of some parameters like working temperature and pressure, and thermal conductance on the performance of the hybrid system have been investigated which are not taken into account in the previous works. Additionally, system assessment from an economic viewpoint is not considered in the past studies. Finally, the techno-economic betterment of the system through multi-objective

optimization has not been presented in the previously published studies. By solving the optimization problem, scholars and industrial experts will gain a wide perspective of the system and its developed aspects.

Therefore in a brief view next to this section, the paper includes a description of methods in Section 2, an explanation of the system in Section 2.1, energy analysis in Section 2.2, exergy analysis in Section 2.3, exergoeconomic analysis in Section 2.4, description of multi-objective optimization in Section 2.5, the results presentation in Section 3, validation of the results in Section 3.1, discussion in Section 4 which concerns parametric investigations (Section 4.1) and an optimization solution (Section 4.2) and conclusions with some recommendations for future works in Section 5.

2. Methods

2.1. Explanation of the System

Figures 1 and 2 illustrate a diagram of the integrated system. The aforementioned system comprises an MCFC to generate electricity and waste heat via converting the chemical energy of a fuel (natural gas) into electricity, and a TEG to generate surplus power by utilizing a chunk of the fuel cell exhaust gases (Q_H) at a temperature of T and one regenerator to compensate the regenerative losses of another part of waste heat (Q_r). The latest chunk of waste heat (Q) is discharged. Moreover, Q_L in Figure 1 is the heat transfer rate of the thermoelectric generator cold connection to the ambient. To implement the hybrid system, the following presumptions were considered:

- Operation of MCFC and TEG under steady-state conditions [1].
- MCFC works under constant and uniform working temperature and pressure [1].
- Reactants are considered ideal gases, and all of them are utilized by MCFC [77].
- Ignoring the electrical power consumption of the utilities of the MCFC sub-system [78].

Figure 1. Schematic diagrams of the hybrid system.

Figure 2. Procedure flow diagram of the hybrid system.

2.1.1. Molten Carbonate Fuel Cell

A blend of molten carbonate salts utilizes in the electrolyte of this kind of fuel cell, which combines lithium carbonate and sodium carbonate or lithium carbonate plus potassium carbonate [79,80]. To provide a suitable condition for carbonate melting and obtain better electrolyte conductivity in MCFC, mentioned fuel cell works at high temperatures (600–700 °C) [80]. The carbonate (CO_3^{2-}) is the conductor ion in the MCFC. These ions are sent toward the employed anode which is sent from the cathode part [81]. In the anode, according to the reaction of $\text{H}_2 + \text{CO}_3^{2-} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2 + 2\text{e}^-$, H_2 reacts with carbonate ions and generates CO_2 , H_2O , and electrons. Electrons are sent into the external circuit to generate power. Based on the reaction $\frac{1}{2}\text{O}_2 + \text{CO}_2 + 2\text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{CO}_3^{2-}$ in the cathode, O_2 reacts with CO_2 to generate carbonate's ions [33,34]. The net reaction occurring in the MCFC is as follows [82–84]:

The reaction happening in the reformer ($\text{CH}_4 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 4\text{H}_2 + \text{CO}_2$), supply the needed H_2 for the process [85–87]. Moreover, to define the electrochemical concept of the fuel cell and ascertain the voltage generated by the fuel cell unit (V_{cell}) Nernst equation is used. However, due to the irreversible losses, the value of mentioned voltage is significantly lower [75]. Table 1 reports mentioned losses and their formulas.

Table 1. Useable equations for MCFC electrochemical simulation.

Item	Relation	Ref.
Fuel cell voltage	$V_{Cell} = E - (U_{anode} + U_{cathode} + U_{ohmic})$	[87]
Cell potential equilibrium	$E = \frac{242000 - 45.8T}{nF} + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln\left(\frac{P_{H2,anode} P_{CO2,cathode} (P_{O2,cathode})^{0.5}}{P_{H2O,anode} P_{CO2,anode}}\right)$	[88]
Anode overpotential	$U_{anode} = 22.7 \times 10^{-10} j \exp\left(\frac{E_{act,anode}}{RT}\right) \times P_{H2,anode}^{-0.4} P_{CO2,anode}^{-0.17} P_{H2O,anode}^{-1}$	[89]
Cathode overpotential	$U_{cathode} = 75 \times 10^{-11} j \exp\left(\frac{E_{act,cathode}}{RT}\right) \times P_{O2,cathode}^{-0.43} P_{CO2,cathode}^{-0.19}$	[89]
Ohmic overpotential	$U_{ohmic} = 5 \times 10^{-5} j \exp\left(3016\left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{923}\right)\right)$	[89]

Besides, Table 2 demonstrates the parameters needed for the simulation.

Table 2. Required input data for simulation.

Parameter	Value	Ref.
Working temperature, (C)	650	[1]
Working pressure, (atm)	1	[1]
Anode activation energy, (J/mol)	53,500	[1]
Cathode activation energy, (J/mol)	77,300	[1]
Reference Temperature, (C)	25	[76]
Conductivity of heat, (W/k·m)	0.02	[78]
Thermoelectric materia figure of merit	1	
Anode gas composition		[78]
Hydrogen: 0.6, Carbon dioxide: 0.15, water: 0.25		
Cathode gas composition Nitrogen: 0.59, Carbon dioxide: 0.08, water: 0.25, Oxygen: 0.08		[78]

The generated electricity and the efficiency of the cell can be considered as two pivotal factors for evaluating the electrochemical model of the MCFC, which are achieved by the following relations, respectively [90,91]:

$$P_{fuelcell} = A \times j \times V_{cell} \quad (2)$$

$$\eta_{fuelcell} = \frac{n_e \times F}{-\Delta h} \times V_{cell} \quad (3)$$

Which A , j , n_e , F , and $-\Delta h$ denote an active area of the cell, current density, number of the transferred electrons ($n_e = 2$), Faraday constant ($F = 96,487 \text{ C/mol}$), and changes in molar enthalpy of the electrochemical reaction, respectively.

2.1.2. Thermoelectric Generator

Bypassing the Q_H toward the cold connection (Q_L) in a TEG, an electrical current is produced (Figure 2) [71]. P and N-type semiconductor legs have been linked in parallel and series for a TEG unit [60,76]. In this paper, it is assumed that [1,76]:

- MCFC output temperature is equal to hot junction's one.
- The ambient temperature is equal to the old junction one.
- Thermal conductivity, electrical resistance, and the See-beck coefficient are not dependent on the temperature.

The two equations to define the corresponding losses can be considered according to Joule and Fourier heat as [28]:

$$Q_H = \alpha I_g T - 0.5 I_g^2 R + K(T - T_0) \quad (4)$$

$$Q_L = \alpha I_g T + 0.5 I_g^2 R + K(T - T_0) \quad (5)$$

where α , I_g and R denote the Seebeck coefficient, electrical current, and resistance, respectively. The values of R and α can then be defined as [1]:

$$R = \left[\frac{\rho_P I_P}{S_P} + \frac{\rho_n I_n}{S_n} \right] \times m \quad (6)$$

$$\alpha = [\alpha_P + \alpha_n] \times m \quad (7)$$

where m represents the number of connected TEGs. Based on the thermodynamics' first law, the generated electricity of the TEG may be measured utilizing the following relation [76]:

$$P_{TEG} = Q_H - Q_L = K \times i \times (T - T_0) - \frac{K \times i^2}{Z} \quad (8)$$

Another relation illustrates how to measure the productivity of the TEG [1]:

$$\eta_{TEG} = \frac{P_{TEG}}{Q_H} = \frac{Z \times i \times (T - T_0) - i^2}{Z \times (T - T_0) + (Z \times T \times i) - \frac{i^2}{2}} \quad (9)$$

The figure of merit and current density is given by [30]:

$$i = \frac{\alpha \times I_g}{K} \quad (10)$$

$$Z = \frac{\alpha^2}{K \times R} \quad (11)$$

2.1.3. Regenerator

In this study, a heat exchanger is used as a regenerator, which preheats the inlet reactants by a fraction of waste heat of the exhaust products, and has been determined by the following equation [79,86]:

$$q_r = K_{re} \times A_{re} \times (1 - \beta) \times (T - T_0) \quad (12)$$

where, K_{re} and A_{re} are the coefficient and area of heat transfer, respectively.

2.2. Energy Analysis

In Figure 1, trusted on the first law of thermodynamics we have [79]:

$$Q_H = -\Delta H - P_{fuelcell} - q_{re} - q$$

$$= \frac{-A\Delta h}{n_e F} \left[\left(1 - \eta_{fuelcell} \right) \times j - \frac{n_e F \times (c_1 + c_2) (T - T_0)}{-\Delta h} \right] \quad (13)$$

$$q = \alpha_L \times A_L \times (T - T_0) \quad (14)$$

where α_L and A_L denote coefficients of the heat loss and heat transfer area. Additionally, c_1 and c_2 are two parameters that are regenerative losses and the heat leakage, sequentially and have been circumscribed by the next equations [79]:

$$c_1 = \frac{K_{re} \times A_{re} \times (1 - \beta)}{A} \quad (15)$$

$$c_2 = \frac{\alpha_L \times A_L}{A} \quad (16)$$

TEG may not operate in the suggested system with MCFC under all conditions, as some circumstances should be met as [79,87]:

$$-\Delta H - P_{fuelcell} \geq q_{re} + q + K(T - T_0) \quad (17)$$

According to the previous relationship, the above equation can be rewritten as follows [79]:

$$j > j_C = \left[\frac{n_e \times F}{-\Delta h \times (1 - \eta_{fuelcell})} \right] \times \left[(c_1 + c_2)(T - T_0) + \frac{K \times (T - T_0)}{A} \right] \quad (18)$$

On the other word, operating rang of the TEG can be calculated as $j_C < j < j_M$, where j_C/j_M refer to the lower and upper bounds. The next equation states the correlation between the current density and current of the TEG [78]:

$$i^2 - [2 \times Z \times T \times i] - 2Z \times (T - T_0) + \frac{Z \times A}{K} \times \left[\frac{-\Delta h}{F} \times j \times (1 - \eta_{fuelcell}) - (c_1 + c_2)(T - T_0) \right] = 0 \quad (19)$$

Therefore, for the following two circumstances, we can measure the electricity and efficiency of the suggested plant [78]:

$$\text{if } j_C < j < j_M : \begin{cases} P_{Hybrid} = P_{fuelcell} + K \times T_0 \times \left[i \times \left(\frac{T}{T_0} - 1 \right) - \frac{i^2}{ZT_0} \right] \\ \eta_{Hybrid} = \eta_{fuelcell} + \frac{n_e \times F \times K \times T_0 \times \left[i \times \left(\frac{T}{T_0} - 1 \right) - \frac{i^2}{ZT_0} \right]}{-j \times A \times \Delta h} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

$$\text{if } j < j_C \text{ or } j > j_M : \begin{cases} P_{Hybrid} = P_{fuelcell} \\ \eta_{Hybrid} = \eta_{fuelcell} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

Results of the energy analysis confirm that at a current density of 3000 A/m² by one MCFC and one TEG the produced electricity of MCFC, TEG, and suggested plant are 1247.3 W, 8.37 W, and 1255.67 W, respectively. Furthermore, their efficiencies are 47.3%, 22.42%, and 38%, respectively.

2.3. Exergy Analysis

Second law analysis is classified into three main levels:

- For a plant: measuring of total irreversibility and 2nd rule efficiency [92].
- For the elements of the plant: Irreversibility and 2nd rule efficiency [93].
- For stream materials: Measuring different kinds of exergy to calculate total exergy

By ignoring the kinetic and potential exergy and summing up the physical and chemical exergy we have [94–97]:

$$\dot{E} = \dot{E}_{ch} + \dot{E}_{ph} \quad (22)$$

where

$$\dot{E}_{ch} = \sum_k x_k e_k^{ch} + RT_0 \sum_k x_k \ln x_k \quad (23)$$

$$\dot{E}_{ph} = (h - h_0) - T_0(s - s_0) \quad (24)$$

To exergy analysis, we first consider the thermodynamic model of the hybrid system. The process streams compositions are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. The compounds of each process flow.

Flow	Argon	Methane	Etane	Propan	n-Butane	Carbon-Monoxide	Carbon-Dioxide	Hydrogen	Water	Nitrogen	Oxygen	Carbonate
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
2	0	0.7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0
3	0	0.7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0
4	0	0.2	0	0	0	0.2	0	0.6	0	0	0	0
5	0	0.2	0	0	0	0.2	0	0.5	0	0	0	0
6	0	0.2	0	0	0	0.2	0	0.5	0	0	0	0
7	0	0.2	0	0	0	0.2	0	0.5	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	0.2	0
9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	0.2	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	0.2	0
11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	0.2	0
12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	0.2	0
13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	0.2	0
14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	0.2	0
15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	0.2	0
16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	0.2	0
17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	0.2	0
19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	0.2	0
21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
22	0	0.2	0	0	0	0.2	0	0.6	0	0	0	0
23	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	0.2	0
24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	0.2	0
Naturalgas	0	0.9	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Air	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.01	0.77	0.21	0
Water	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0

2.3.1. Exergy Investigation of MCFC

For calculation of the exergy rate of the MCFC the following relation can be used [89]:

$$\dot{E}_{D,MCFC} = j \times A \times \left(\frac{-\Delta h}{n_e F} - V_{cell} \right) \quad (25)$$

Additionally, the next equation can be used to calculate the exergy rate of the MCFC [98]:

$$\dot{E}_{D,MCFC} = \sum \dot{E}_{in} - \sum \dot{E}_{out} \quad (26)$$

where, E_{in} and E_{out} are input and output exergies, sequentially. Exergetic efficiency of the MCFC is given by [88,90]:

$$\eta_{II,MCFC} = \frac{P_{MCFC}}{\dot{E}_{fuel}} \quad (27)$$

2.3.2. Exergy Investigation of TEG

Trusted on the exoreversible thermodynamic model in the TEG the input and output exergies to/of the system are the thermal exergy and the electrical power, respectively. Therefore, matching to the thermodynamic laws, exergetic balance in TEG may be obtained as below [98,99]:

$$\dot{E}_{in} = \dot{E}_{out} + \dot{E}_{D,TEG} \rightarrow Q_H \times \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T} \right) = P_{TEG} + \dot{E}_D \quad (28)$$

The irreversibilities are obtained by the following equation [100,101]:

$$\dot{E}_D = T_0 \times S_{gen} \quad (29)$$

$$S_{gen} = \frac{Q_L}{T_0} - \frac{Q_H}{T_0} \quad (30)$$

Additionally, the next relation may be applied to determine TEG exergy efficiency [79]:

$$\eta_{II,TEG} = 1 - \frac{\dot{E}_D}{Q_H \times \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T}\right)} \quad (31)$$

Table 4 shows the required equations for determining the second law efficiency and irreversibility of the regenerator, reformer, and catalytic burner.

Table 4. Governing equations for exergy destruction and exergy efficiency measurements.

Elements	Exergetic Study	Exergy Destruction
Regenerator	$1 - \left(\left(\frac{\sum E}{\sum m \Delta h} \right)_h - \left(\frac{\sum E}{\sum m \Delta h} \right)_c \right)$	$(\sum E)_{in} - (\sum E)_{out}$
Catalyst burner and Reformer	$\frac{\sum (me)_{out}}{\sum (me)_{in}}$	$(\sum E)_{in} - (\sum E)_{out}$

2.4. Exergoeconomic Analysis

Through uniting the exergetic study with the economic investigation for all subsystems and elements, the entire cycle the economic objectives of the system have been explained. Cost balance relations are indicated for all elements concerning the estimated stream's exergy. Other auxiliary relations are also included to determine the cost balance relations concurrently. Cost balance has been expressed as [102–105]:

$$\dot{C}_{q,k} + \sum \dot{C}_{in,k} + \dot{Z}_{tot}^{CI+OM} = \dot{C}_{w,k} + \sum \dot{C}_{out,k} \quad (32)$$

Here $\dot{C}$ refers to the rate of cost and $\dot{Z}$ signifies the rate of the cost concerning capital investment plus maintenance. The rate of cost is formulated by [102–104]:

$$\dot{C} = c \times \dot{E} \quad (33)$$

Here c indicates the exergy-specific cost in the unit of USD/GJ. The cost rate of exergy destruction is represented as [102–104]:

$$\dot{C}_D = c_F \times \dot{E}_{F,k} \quad (34)$$

Which c_F signifies the fuel cost. The total rate of cost for the k th element has been expressed below [102–104]:

$$\dot{Z}_k^{CI+OM} = \dot{Z}_k^{CI} + \dot{Z}_k^{OM} \quad (35)$$

Capital investment cost rate of the k th component is given by [102–104]:

$$\dot{Z}_k^{CI+OM} = \left[\frac{CRF \times \phi}{N} \right] Z_k \quad (36)$$

In Equation (36), ϕ is the parameter of maintenance (considered to be 1.06 during the current work) and N indicates the working years of the system. The factor of the capital recovery (CRF) has been exposed as [102–104]:

$$CRF = \frac{i_r \times (1 + i_r)^n}{(1 + i_r)^n - 1} \quad (37)$$

In Equation (37), n and i_r mention the working time number (20 years) and rate of interest (assumed to be 0.15). The total rate of cost for all elements is switched to the existing

year by using the Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index (CEPCI). For all elements, the exergoeconomic factor is provided by [102–104]:

$$f_k = \frac{\dot{Z}_k^{CI+OM}}{\dot{Z}_k^{CI+OM} + \dot{C}_D + \dot{C}_L} \quad (38)$$

This $\dot{C}_L$ represents the cost of exergy loss which is defined as:

$$\dot{C}_L = c_F \times \dot{E}_{loss} \quad (39)$$

Finally, the total rate of cost and cost of the product are described as:

$$\dot{C}_{tot} = \sum_i \dot{Z}_i + \dot{C}_{fuel} \quad (40)$$

$$c_{P,tot} = \frac{\dot{C}_{tot}}{\dot{E}_{Product}} \quad (41)$$

2.5. Multi-Objective Optimization

Toward the intention of optimization of inconsistent objective functions like cost and thermodynamic efficacy, multi-objective optimization is required. Consequently, optimal non-prevail solutions are collected in a Pareto frontier to impersonate a curve containing optimal spots. The most powerful decision parameters are picked as the optimization input [105–108]. Optimization may be carried by employing different algorithms. The genetic evolutionary algorithm has perpetually been an appropriate option due to its remarkable convergence in systems optimization [109]. In the current work, exergy efficiency and product cost are considered as objective functions and EES software has been linked with MATLAB software to carry the optimization through the genetic algorithm toolbox of MATLAB. The genetic algorithm is used for system optimization and a similar approach is taken into account as described in Ref [100–110]. The population size of 100 besides 10 generations, Crossover, and mutation of 85% and 1% have been deemed to carry the optimization. Ultimately, the amounts of key variables are determined at those points, and the criteria functions are placed together. Furthermore, the scattered arrangement of the inlet parameters is implemented within the planned decision variables boundaries [111–115]. The decision variables boundaries employed toward the optimization are: $500 < j \text{ (A/m}^2\text{)} < 6000$, $600 < T \text{ (}^\circ\text{C)} < 700$, and $1 < P \text{ (bar)} < 3$.

3. Results

In this section, the outcomes of the newly introduced hybrid MCFC/TEG system simulation are presented. The thermodynamic properties for each state are listed in Table 5.

Table 5. The thermodynamic properties of each process flow.

Flow	T (C)	P (bar)	m. (kg/s)
1	103.7	1.1	0.42
2	69.6	1.1	19.25
3	549.6	1.1	0.42
4	790	1.03	0.42
5	790	1.03	1.5
6	790	1.03	1.5
7	790	1.03	1.51

Table 5. Cont.

Flow	T (C)	P (bar)	m. (kg/s)
8	640	1.03	0
9	648.9	1.03	0.002
10	648.9	1.03	1.405
12	640	1.03	64,285
13	640	1.03	0
14	640	1.03	584
15	640	1.03	63,718
16	640	1.03	63,718
17	651.1	1.03	0.01
18	640	1.03	64,290
19	651.1	1.03	0.01
20	648.5	1.01	584
21	648.4	1.01	584
22	660	1.03	1.384
23	648.5	1.01	585
24	25	1.01	585
Natural gas	16	3.13	1
Air	16	1.15	19.23
Water	33	3.13	0.42

The physical and chemical exergy rates of the state points are listed in Table 6.

Table 6. The physical and chemical exergy rates of the state points.

Flow	$\dot{E}_{ph}$ (MW)	$\dot{E}_{ch}$ (MW)
1	0.20	0.01
2	0.09	48.24
3	0.98	48.24
4	1.94	51.3
5	0	0
6	0.002	0.06
7	2.1	51.22
8	20,504	904.55
9	20,503	904.52
10	0	0
11	20,500	904.53
12	20.5	905
13	0	0
14	186.1	8.2
15	20,324	896.4
16	20,323	896.4
17	0.013	0.0001
18	20,504	904.5
19	0.013	0.0001
20	185.1	8.2
21	185.2	8.2
22	1.43	51.2
23	186.1	58.1
24	-0.17	57.8
Natural gas	156.8	48.3
Air	0.2	46.1
Water	0.2	0.01

Table 7 presents the results of the exergy analysis. Furthermore, according to the equation ($\dot{E}_D = \text{Summation of whole components exergy destruction}$), the total hybrid system exergy destruction is 17,705 kW.

Table 7. Exergetic investigation outcomes.

Elements	Exergy Destruction (MW)	Exergetic Efficiency (%)
MCFC	13.9	69
TEG	0.27	97.4
Regenerator	1.5	81.3
Catalyst burner	1.1	99.5
Reformer	0.9	62.4

3.1. Validation of the Results

To verify the simulating code's accuracy, the current density and voltage are determined as a contender to be compared with the consequences accomplished by an earlier published study. The design variations are similar to the data published by [38] which have been shown in Table 8. The obtained results in the current work are in corroborate Ref. [38] and verify the accuracy of the simulating codes.

Table 8. Validation and comparison between the current study and published work.

Current Density (A/cm ²)	Voltage (V)	Voltage (V) (This Study)	Error (%)
80.4225	408.308	410.091	−0.436
82.6452	407.231	412.301	−1.245
85.1665	406.154	405.747	0.100
90.1975	403.231	405.101	−0.463
93.9104	402	403.61	−0.4024
96.5763	400.615	403.233	−0.653
100.425	398.462	396.659	0.4524
103.972	396.154	398.134	−0.500
108.106	393.077	394.480	−0.356
112.386	389.846	388.403	0.370
116.076	387.077	388.336	−0.325
120.057	383.846	385.600	−0.456

4. Discussions

4.1. Parametric Investigations

Toward electricity production, the fuel cell voltage current of the thermoelectric generator is a significant factor. Different operating temperatures are considered to evaluate the operation of this system as illustrated in Figure 3. An increment of the current density reduces the cell voltage but cell voltage improves with temperature. For example, at $j = 3000 \text{ A/m}^2$ the output cell voltage for temperatures of 600 °C, 650 °C, and 700 °C is 0.4004, 0.5965, and 0.7008, respectively. Furthermore, the electrical current of the thermoelectric generator enhances by growing the current density and diminishing the operating temperature. Note that, until $j = 2200 \text{ A/m}^2$ for $T = 600 \text{ °C}$, $j = 2800 \text{ A/m}^2$ for $T = 650 \text{ °C}$ and $j = 3200 \text{ A/m}^2$ for $T = 750 \text{ °C}$, the electrical current is zero.

The power of working pressure on the cell voltage and electrical current has been illustrated in Figure 4. The cell voltage increases by pressure but the electrical current decreases.

Figure 3. Impact of operating temperature on the cell voltage and the dimensionless electrical current at various current densities.

Figure 4. Impact of operating pressure on the cell voltage and the dimensionless electrical current at various current densities.

Figure 5 illustrates the efficiency and outlet electricity of the fuel cell, thermoelectric generator, and suggested system at various current densities. P_{MCFC} , P_{TEG} , and the net power of hybrid system increases by current density firstly, then decreases, which means that it is better to use MCFC and TEG at a specific working range of the current density. As it can be observed, with improving the current density, MCFC, TEG, and hybrid efficiencies decrease, but at optimum current density ($2800 < j < 3780 \text{ A/m}^2$) efficiency increases. The highest outlet electricity of the hybrid system is at $j = 3000 \text{ A/m}^2$ and equal to 5163.9 kW.

Figure 5. Output power and efficiency of MCFC, TEG, and hybrid system at various current densities of the MCFC.

The outlet electricity of the system and its efficiency is influenced by the temperature and pressure of the proposed configuration as illustrated in Figures 6 and 7. Outlet electricity of the offered system improves through growing the temperature or pressure. The highest output electricity is obtained at a temperature of 650 °C, 3 atm, and $j = 4600 \text{ A/m}^2$ resulting in 8091.9 kW. Furthermore, the system's efficiency increases by increasing the temperature or pressure. For example, at $j = 3000 \text{ A/m}^2$ the system's efficiency for temperatures of 600, 650, and 700 °C is gained 33.84%, 46.32%, and 47.96%, respectively. Moreover, at the pressures of 1, 2, and 3 bar the efficiency is gained 46.32%, 50.57%, and 51.95%, respectively. In other words, at $j = 3000 \text{ A/m}^2$, the highest efficiency is obtained at 650 °C and 3 bar.

Figure 6. The impact of working temperature on the outlet electricity of the hybrid system at various current densities.

Figure 7. The impact of working temperature and pressure on the hybrid system efficiency at various current densities.

Thermal conductance would be influential within the range of $j_C < j < j_M$ and by improving K , the outlet electricity and efficiency of the suggested plant improve. This issue is demonstrated in Figures 8 and 9. For example, thermal conductivity changes from 0.02 to 0.04, at $j = 3000 \text{ A/m}^2$, the outlet electricity and plant's productivity improve by 4% and 4.3%, respectively.

Figure 8. The impact of thermal conductivity on the outlet electricity of the hybrid system at various current densities.

Figure 9. The impact of thermal conductivity on the efficiency of the hybrid system at various current densities.

The impact of ZT0 alteration on the electricity and system's efficiency is illustrated in Figures 10 and 11, respectively. Mentioned change is not so important, for instance, with an alteration in the figure of merit in the range of 1–1.4, the outlet electricity and efficiency improves only 0.02% and 0.3%.

Figure 10. The impact of a figure of merit on the outlet electricity of the hybrid system at various current densities.

Figure 11. The impact of outlet electricity of different ZT0 at various current densities.

Concerning investigating the impact of the changes in constants c_1 and c_2 on the electricity and efficiency of the suggested unit, we consider alterations in the range of $j_C < j < j_M$. Variation in generated electricity and productivity of the suggested plant in this current density interval are shown in Figures 12 and 13, respectively. When increasing constants c_1 and c_2 , efficiency and outlet electricity of the hybrid system increases. When $c_1 = c_2 = 1$ is replaced by $c_1 = c_2 = 0.1$ at the current density of 3000 A/m^2 , output power and efficacy increase by 1.5% and 29.7%, respectively. Furthermore, $c_1 = 0, c_2 = 0.1$ and $c_1 = 0.1, c_2 = 0$ have similar results.

Figure 12. The impact of constants c_1 and c_2 on the outlet electricity of the hybrid system at various current densities.

Figure 13. The impact of constants c_1 and c_2 on the efficiency of the hybrid system at various current densities.

For exergy examination purposes, exergy destruction of the MCFC at different operating temperatures and pressures are obtained. The results for temperature and pressure are shown in Figure 14. MCFC exergy destruction increases with current density but decreases with operating temperature and pressure. When the temperature rises by 100 °C, MCFC exergy destruction decreases by 53.6%. Moreover, when the pressure rises by 2 atm, MCFC exergy destruction decreases by 28.9%.

Figure 14. The impact of operating temperature on MCFC exergy destruction.

Figure 15 illustrate the exergy destruction of the TEG in the different operating temperatures. Exergy destruction of the TEG, except its working range, is constant in all regions of the current density at any temperature, and only in the working area of the TEG, exergy destruction increases with temperature.

Figure 15. The impact of constant's working temperature on TEG exergy destruction at various current densities.

According to the next figure (Figure 16), it is clear that TEG exergy efficiency decreases by operating temperature variation. However, this reduction in exergy efficiency is not remarkable.

Figure 16. The impact of operating temperature on TEG exergy efficiency.

The results of thermoeconomic optimization are provided in Figures 17–19. As may be understood, with rising the current density, the total cost of the product diminishes which relates to the higher outlet electricity of the system. There is also an optimal spot in the matter of the total product cost at $J = 3500 \text{ A/m}^2$ at the pressure of 2 bars. However, the higher current density increases total product cost dramatically as the investment cost

of the components increase. Similar trends are seen for different operating temperatures, but the optimum total product cost at the temperature of 700 °C occurs at $J = 4000 \text{ A/m}^2$.

Figure 17. The impact of current density at $T = 600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ on the total product cost and cost rate of the system.

Figure 18. The impact of current density at $T = 650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ on the total product cost and cost rate of the system.

Figure 19. The impact of current density at $T = 700\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ on the total cost of the product and system cost rate.

4.2. Multi-Criteria Optimization Results

The Pareto frontier including optimal spots has been presented in Figure 20. A couple of opposing criteria would rise by growing each of them. Several circumstances have been deduced and can be regarded for planning the systems relying on the perspective of technicians and stakeholders. Nevertheless, the favorable working spots would be contrasted to the ideal solution point which is exposed in the Pareto front. Three various working points are chosen which have distinct thermodynamic efficiency and total rate of cost.

Figure 20. Pareto optimum solution spots of the offered system.

The decision variable amounts linked to those points accompanying the amounts of the criteria functions have been presented in Table 9.

Table 9. Criteria functions and decision variables for optimization.

Variables		Criteria Functions		
Pressure (bar)	Current Density (A/m ²)	Temperature (C)	Cost (\$/GJ)	Exergetic Efficiency (%)
Least cost 1.5	3498	649	24.2	64.19
Optimal 2.1	4199	679	29.9	70.1
Maximum exergetic efficiency 3	5398	698	55.1	79.9
Ideal point	-	-	24.2	79.9

A scatter arrangement of the picked decision parameters would be addressed and interpreted to signal the planners what can be the most suitable working area of mentioned parameters. Referring to Figure 21, in the prepared variety of population, the fuel cell inlet pressure has not special good working area since optimal solutions have not been constrained in a particular area. However, the optimal solutions as outcomes of changing the MCFC outlet temperature are largely positioned at the underside of the investigated range that indicating that the aforementioned variable should be held either in the maximum or minimum value. As illustrated in Figure 19, the current density should not be higher than 5000 A/m² as a few solution points are located at this range.

Figure 21. Cont.

Figure 21. Scatter plots of inlet parameters.

5. Conclusions

This paper investigated energy and exergy aspects of a hybrid system consisting of a molten carbonate fuel cell (MCFC) plus a thermoelectric generator (TEG). Computational simulation and thermodynamic investigation of the hybrid system were carried out utilizing MATLAB and HYSYS software, respectively. The electricity provided by the MCFC and the TEG is 1247.3 W and 8.37 W, sequentially. The results demonstrate that the outlet electricity and productivity of the hybrid system are 1255.67 W and 38%, respectively. Exergy study results revealed that exergy destruction of the MCFC and TEG is 13,945.9 kW and 262.75 kW, respectively. Furthermore, their exergy efficiency is 68.22% and 97.31%, respectively. Sensitivity analysis showed the following results:

- Cell voltage decreases by current density and increases with operating temperature. Furthermore, the dimensionless electrical current of TEG improves by improving current density and reducing operating temperature.
- With increasing current density, P_{MCFC} , P_{TEG} and net electricity of the hybrid system first raise then reduces. Moreover, with growing current density, fuel cell, thermoelectric generator, and hybrid system efficiencies decrease, but at optimum j ($2800 < j < 3780 \text{ A/m}^2$), efficiency increases.
- Alteration of thermal conductivity is influential in region $j_C < j < j_M$ and by improving K , the outlet electricity and efficiency of the hybrid system improve.
- Exergy destruction of the TEG, except its working range, is constant in all regions of the current density at any temperature, and only in the working area of the TEG, with increasing temperature, the exergy destruction also increases.

The optimization outcomes reveal that in the final optimum solution point, the exergetic efficiency and total cost of the product are determined at 70% and 30 USD/GJ.

Some recommendations for future works are counseled as follows:

- The suggested integrated systems in the current research have enough flexibility to work with other energy reservoirs such as solar energy and biomass. Advancing this idea can grow the reliability and independence of the recommended configuration.
- There is an overabundance of tools for the deep investigation of innovative energy systems. On top of the approaches, energy investigations and advanced assessments are proposed for scholars in future works. Introduced approaches hold deeper features to inquire about energy systems and can accommodate further information for scholars.
- Adjusting a unit to convert a part of the produced hydrogen and oxygen into hydrogen-peroxide can be regarded as an alluring opportunity for further industrial use.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, R.S. and F.A.T.; methodology, M.K.M.N.; software, R.S.; validation, M.N., M.M.N. and R.S.; formal analysis, M.M.N.; investigation, F.A.T.; resources, F.A.T.; data curation, M.K.M.N.; writing—original draft preparation, A.D.; writing—review and editing, M.M.N.; visualization, R.S.; supervision, M.N.; project administration, A.D.; funding acquisition, M.N. and M.M.N. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Nomenclature

A	Area: m^2
c	Cost, $\$/\text{Gj}$

D	Destruction
E	Ideal voltage of the cell, V
E.	Exergy rate, MW
F	Faraday constant, -/fuel
Δh	Molar enthalpy change, J/mol
i	Dimensionless current,
j	Current density, Am^{-2}
K	Coefficient of heat transfer, $\text{J}/\text{m}^2\text{Ks}$
MCFC	Molten carbonate fuel cell
m	TEG number,
N	Cell number
T	Temperature, C
P	Power, MW; pressure, bar
P_{kth}	K_{th} element partial pressure
Q	Rate of heat transfer, kW
R	Universal gas constant, $\text{J}/\text{mol.K}$
S	Entropy, $\text{KJ}/\text{kgmoleC}$
TEC	Thermoelectric cooler
TEG	Thermoelectric generator
U	Over-potential, v
V	Voltage, v
Z	The figure of merit, $1/\text{K}$
x_i	Molar fraction
η	Efficiency, %
α	Coefficient of Seebeck, v/k
β	Efficiency of regenerator
Subscript	
0	Reference condition
acta	Activation
ch	Chemical
D	Destruction
gen	Generation
in	inlet
n	N-type of semiconductor
ohm	ohmic
out	outlet
ph	Physical

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